

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NOVELS DEDICATED TO ALISHER NAVOI BY OYBEK AND ISAJON SULTAN

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Abstract. *The image of Alisher Navoi has been written many times in Uzbek literature in different types and genres. Poems, epics, drama, story, novel were created about Navoi. The novel is a very complex genre. Of course, Alisher Navoi, a great literary personality and a great public figure, a great creator who showed the beauty of the Turkish language to the world, composed thousands of verses in this language, created 5 epics and many other didactic, memoir and scientific works, is one novel. not for, it can easily be the basis for dozens of novels.*

Key words. *Alisher Navoi, Ulug' Watan, Aibek, Isajon Sultan, Baqi Darbadar, Abdurrahman Jami, Lutfi, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Sultan Hossein Boykara, Nizamulmulk, Majdiddin, Pahlavon Muhamamad, Syed Hasan Ardasher, Sheikh Bahlul, Binai.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РОМАНОВ, ПОСВЯЩЕННЫХ АЛИШЕРУ НАВОИ, НАПИСАННЫХ ОЙБЕКОВ И ИСАДЖОНОМ СУЛТАНОМ

Аннотация. *Образ Алишера Навои неоднократно писался в узбекской литературе в разных видах и жанрах. О Навои созданы стихи, былины, драмы, повести, роман. Роман — очень сложный жанр. Безусловно, Алишер Навои, великая литературская личность и великий общественный деятель, великий творец, явивший миру красоту тюркского языка, сочинивший на этом языке тысячи стихов, создавший 5 былин и многие другие дидактические, мемуарные и научные произведения, это один роман. не для, она легко может стать основой для десятков романов.*

Ключевые слова. *Алишер Навои, Улуг Ватан, Айбек, Исаджон Султан, Баки Дарбадар, Абдурахман Джами, Лютфи, Шарафуддин Али Язди, Султан Хоссейн Бойкара, Низамулмулк, Мадждиддин, Пахлавон Мухамамад, Сайед Хасан Ардашер, Шейх Бахлул, Бинай.*

INTRODUCTION

During the Great Patriotic War in the last century, Oybek, one of the greatest creators of new Uzbek prose, created the novel "Navoiy". Zarifa Saidnosirova, the writer's wife, gave information about the process of creating the novel in her memoir "Oybegim Mening". Almost all of us know these memories. That is, during the war, Oybek eats only half a spoonful of ground rice while sitting hungry, until the end of this novel. Oibek's novel "Navoi" served our people for many years. A series of video films was made based on the work. It is no exaggeration to say that this book and movie are read and watched in every Uzbek's home. Oibek's novel "Navoi" was created in the 40s of the last century and to some extent carried the sociological ideals of the government of the Shura era. Historical facts were adapted to Soviet ideology based on the socialist creative method. That's why there was a need to recreate the life and work of Alisher Navoi, as well as a complicated period in which Navoi lived, that is, the era of the king and poet Sultan Husayn Boygaro, based on the new ideology of independence. This situation has matured.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

As we can see, Isajon Sultan Navoi deeply studied "Qur'an" and Islamic teachings in order to fully reveal his personality and poet's creativity, and then he was able to deeply reveal the great artistic thinking and noble works of the thinker. After all, Shura period was a period in which it was forbidden to study Navoi's work and fully reveal Navoi's personality in literature, and to look at it with Islamic religious knowledge, interpret it, and research it. In this sense, the period of pressure and independent creative freedom of Oybek and Isajon Sultan in creating the image of Navoi differ from each other. But while Aibek lived under the strong pressure of the Shura era, Navoi gave an artistic interpretation of his personality, life and work in accordance with historical facts as much as possible. However, the censors of the Shura era set strict limits for Oybek. In this sense, the skilled writer Oybek created a novel in accordance with such social requirements in revealing the relationship between the Timurid dynasty, in particular Sultan Husayn Boykara and Alisher Navoi. For example, in the pages of Oybek's novel "Navoi" when revealing the relationship between Sultan Husayn Boykara and Alisher Navoi, the tendency to contrast the two characters is very strong. By contrasting the two personalities, Oybek tries to glorify Navoi's personality and make him appear bigger. Navoi is depicted on the pages of the novel as a smart, wise, great creator, statesman, leader of the people, patron of young artists and students. On the pages of the novel, Husayn Boykara is artistically expressed in dark colors as a negative person who is addicted to alcohol, shirakayf, and flirts with young girls in the harem. But the government and friendship of Alisher Navoi and Sultan Hossein Boykara, two heroes, one white and one black, or one extremely positive and the other extremely negative, are described in a unique way.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In his novel "Alisher Navoi", Isajon Sultan removed such negative, over-the-top images that were attached to Sultan Husayn Boykara as a black mark, unlike the respected teacher Oybek. Two images drawn by Isajon Sultan's pen, that is, the poet and minister Alisher Navoi and the king and poet Sultan Husayn Boykara, are beautiful historical and life examples of mutual friendship, how much they respect each other, take care of each other, and manage the state based on cooperation and consensus. revealed. When creating the novel "Navoi" and the image of Navoi, both writers deeply studied historical facts, in particular, historical sources reflecting the period Navoi lived, memoirs, especially Navoi's work, and applied them to the historical novel. In particular, hundreds of historical figures such as Abdurahman Jami, Lutfi, Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Sultan Husayn Boykara, Nizamulmulk, Majdiddin, Pahlavon Muhamamad, Syed Hasan Ardasher, Sheikh Bahlul, Binai were brought into the novel. Another difference in the novel of Oybek and Isajon Sultan is the reflection and non-reflection of the image of the harem, in our opinion. In particular, Hazrat Oybek, while creating the motif of love between Dildor and Arslanqul and their textile image in the novel "Navoi", very impressively reflected the events of Dildor's life in the khan's harem, living as a concubine in the service of Princess Khadija Begum, in particular, the tragedies of concubines. Isajon Sultan did not allow such woven images in the novel "Alisher Navoi". Mainly, on the basis of historical and artistic materials, he tried to reveal Navoi's personality and life. In some pages of the novel, there are places where journalistic interpretations have intensified. In our opinion, Isajon Sultan did not set himself the goal of presenting the tragedy of women in the Khanate era, the deep drama of harem girls. In particular, the tragic drama of harem girls in the khan's palace is depicted with extremely high pathos in the works of Abdulla Qadiri, Oybek, Sadridin Ainiy. In the works "Mehrobdan

Chayan", "Navoi", "Esdaliklar" the fate of the girls attracted to the khan, the mysterious life of the girls in the harem are expressed interestingly and impressively. These three writers were more or less aware of the tragedy of women during the Khanate regime and had sufficient knowledge. Isajon Sultan, as a new young artist of the 21st century, did not bring such images related to women with a black background into the novel. Perhaps it was true. Because Isajon Sultan's introduction of the events of the harem and the love story of Dildor and Arslan into his novel, in our eyes, would be a repetition of Oybek.

CONCLUSION

In this sense, Isajon Sultan, on the basis of the historical facts he knew to be true and learned, reflected the image of Alisher Navoi and the color of the historical period in which Navoi lived very deeply. Both writers tried to deeply reflect the reality of the time by deeply studying the historical period and historical conditions in the novel. Isajon Sultan, like Oybek, effectively used the 15th century bookish literary style, Persian-Tajik, archaic, historical words in the text of the novel in order to give a full and convincing historical color. In the text of the novel, Isajon Sultan paid special attention to hundreds of historical conquests, military and national clothes, names of cities and towns, names of historical figures, names of national foods and drinks, names of plants and animals in the Khan's palace and khanate system typical of that period. Of course, in creating this new novel "Alisher Navoi", Isajon Sultan seriously relied on original historical sources (such as "Habib us siyar"), in today's Uzbek novels, he hit the paw of Oibek and based on the new criteria of independence, he justified the personality of Navoi, in particular, the relationship between Navoi and Sultan Husan Boykara. illuminated. Of course, both works will have a special place in the history of our nation. The novels "Navoiy" and "Alisher Navoiy" created with the artistic skills of Oybek and Isajon Sultan will serve the future literary generation. Aybek's novel "Navoi" was translated into more than ten Turkish languages and Russian-European languages. We think that Isajon Sultan's novel, which glorifies the friendship of Navoi and Husayn Boygaro, Navoi's great talent, and ideal morality, will be translated into many foreign languages in the coming years, as well as Oibek's novel. The comparative analysis of the image of Alisher Navoi artistically interpreted in the two novels, the unique creative style and artistic skills of the two creators in presenting historical facts in the context of the work, require separate large-scale scientific research.

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